

KINETIC MODEL OF LEACHING OF NEEDLE-FORM PARTICLES

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The article considers the case of leaching in the kinetic region, while the solid material is considered as a needle-shaped polydisperse material. It is proposed to use the distribution function of the number of particles N along their length l in the form $N=a \cdot l^b$, where a and b are constants. This distribution was used to derive the equation of the process rate W , taking into account the dependence of the particle surface on the degree of leaching α : $W=d\alpha/d\tau=K^* \cdot (1-\alpha)^m \cdot ((C_0(\gamma-\alpha)/\gamma))^n$, where K^* is the rate constant; m and n – order by solid material and solvent, respectively; C_0 and γ are the initial concentration of the solvent and its stoichiometric excess.

Keywords: leaching, distribution function, kinetic equation, reaction order.

1. Introduction

Leaching – extraction of one or more components from solid bodies (ores, concentrates, intermediate products, production waste) with an aqueous solution containing alkali, acid or other reagent. Usually, leaching is accompanied by a chemical reaction, as a result of which the extracted component changes from a water-insoluble form to a soluble one. At the end of leaching, in contrast to dissolution, a solid phase always remains, that is, the degree of leaching is less than 100%. As a rule, crushed material of different granulometric composition is received for leaching. In the process of leaching, the surface of such material changes, which, together with a decrease in the concentration of reagents and the accumulation of products, leads to a decrease in the rate of leaching.

If the leaching reaction is irreversible and is not accompanied by the formation of a shell of a solid product, the leaching rate W can be expressed by the equation:

$$W=-dG/d\tau=K \cdot C^n \cdot S, \quad (1)$$

where G is the mass of the solid phase; τ – reaction time; K is the rate constant; C – reagent concentration; n is the order of the reagent, S is the surface of the solid phase.

The value of the surface depends on the shape of the particles (sphere, cube, plate and needle) of the monodisperse material. In practice, it is often necessary to deal with polydisperse materials with a wide range of particle sizes, while in the process of dissolution, not only the surface of the particles changes, but also their number, since small fractions first dissolve and disappear.

Much and constant attention is paid to the leaching process in the scientific literature [1–3]. From the array of various information, it is possible to conditionally single out works devoted to the course of leaching in the diffusion region [4–7] with the provision of the corresponding kinetic equations. There are also works [8–10] in which the authors note the course of leaching in the kinetic region. The authors of [11] processed the data according to 18 kinetic equations that reflect various mechanisms on a solid material, but do not take into account the influence of the concentration of the solvent.

In article [12], the case of the course of leaching in the kinetic region for a polydisperse material of spherical shape is considered. The process speed equation was obtained, taking into account the dependence of the particle surface on the degree of leaching. It was established that the order of the solid material for polydisperse spherical particles can vary from 2/3 to 1.

We carried out a mathematical justification of the kinetic model of leaching for needle-shaped particles and obtained the following data regarding the type of kinetic equation. The work is given relevance by the use of the distribution function of the number of needle-form particles of solid material along their length to determine the change in the surface of the solid material during the leaching process.

2. Kinetic model

The analysis of equation (1) shows that it is enough to simply take into account the change in the concentration of C of the solvent, and the change in the process of leaching the surface of the solid material is proposed to be carried out as follows.

At the initial mass of the solid phase G_0 at the moment of reaching mass G , the degree of leaching α is equal to:

$$\alpha=(G_0-G)/G_0=1-G/G_0, \text{ whence } G=G_0(1-\alpha) \text{ and } dG=-G_0d\alpha. \quad (2)$$

At the initial concentration of the liquid reagent C_0 , the current concentration is determined as:

$$C=C_0(\gamma-\alpha)/\gamma, \quad (3)$$

where γ is the excess (shortage) of the reagent against stoichiometry; with the stoichiometric ratio $\gamma=1$.

Taking into account expressions (2) and (3), equation (1) takes the form:

$$W=d\alpha/d\tau=K \cdot S \cdot ((C_0(\gamma-\alpha)/\gamma))^n/G_0. \quad (4)$$

To establish the functional dependence between the size of the surface S and the degree of leaching α , we take the needle-like shape of solid particles with a diameter d , the surface of which decreases due to a decrease in their length l and the number of particles N . It is assumed that $l \gg d$. In general, the distribution function can be expressed by the equation:

$$N=a \cdot l^b, \quad (5)$$

where a and b are constants.

If $b=0$, then $N=a=const$, the function is represented by a point and all particles have the same initial

length l_0 . If $0 < b < 1$, then the function (5) is expressed by a convex curve, when $b > 1$ – by a concave curve. If $b = 1$, then the number of particles depends linearly on their length.

Therefore, if the number of particles with a length of l_0 and less is expressed by the function (5), then the number of particles with a length from l to $l + dl$ is equal to:

$$dN = a \cdot b \cdot l^{b-1} \cdot dl. \quad (6)$$

The mass of particles with a length in the interval from l to $l + dl$ is equal to:

$$dG = \pi \cdot (d/2)^2 \cdot l \cdot \rho \cdot dN = \pi \cdot (d/2)^2 \cdot l^b \cdot \rho \cdot a \cdot b \cdot dl, \quad (7)$$

where ρ is the density of the solid material.

The total mass of particles in the limits of integration over l from 0 to l_0 is equal to:

$$G = \pi \cdot (d/2)^2 \cdot \rho \cdot a \cdot b \cdot \int l^b dl = \pi \cdot (d/2)^2 \cdot \rho \cdot a \cdot b \cdot l^{(b+1)/(b+1)}. \quad (8)$$

The initial mass of particles in the limits of integration over l from 0 to l_0 is equal to:

$$G_0 = \pi \cdot (d/2)^2 \cdot \rho \cdot a \cdot b \cdot \int l^b dl = \pi \cdot (d/2)^2 \cdot \rho \cdot a \cdot b \cdot l_0^{(b+1)/(b+1)}. \quad (9)$$

These formulas are valid for all values of b except $b = 0$, since in this case the function (5) has a discontinuity and the total and initial mass of the particles is equal to:

$$G = \pi \cdot (d/2)^2 \cdot \rho \cdot a \cdot l; \quad G_0 = \pi \cdot (d/2)^2 \cdot \rho \cdot a \cdot l_0.$$

Taking into account expressions (8) and (9), the degree of leaching of needle-shaped particles can be expressed in terms of their dimensions l_0 and l :

$$\alpha = (G_0 - G) / G_0 = (l_0^{b+1} - l^{b+1}) / l_0^{b+1} = 1 - l^{b+1} / l_0^{b+1}. \quad (10)$$

From equation (10), we obtain the dependence of the length of the particles on the degree of leaching:

$$l = l_0 (1 - \alpha)^{1/(b+1)}. \quad (11)$$

The surface of particles with a length in the interval from l to $l + dl$, taking into account expression (6), is equal to (neglect the surface of the end faces of the needle):

$$S = \pi \cdot d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot \int l^b dl = \pi \cdot d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot l^{b+1} / (b+1). \quad (12)$$

This formula, like formula (9), is valid for all values of b , except $b = 0$. For $b = 0$, the outer surface of the particles is equal to:

$$S = \pi \cdot d \cdot l \cdot a.$$

Taking into account expression (11), the total surface of all particles:

$$S = \pi \cdot d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot l_0^{(b+1)} \cdot (1 - \alpha) / (b+1). \quad (13)$$

After substituting the initial mass of particles according to equation (9) and the total surface of all particles according to equation (13) into equation (4), we get the leaching rate equation:

$$W = da/d\tau = K^* \cdot ((C_0(\gamma - \alpha)/\gamma))^n \cdot (1 - \alpha), \quad (14)$$

where $K^* = 4K/(d \cdot \rho)$.

With a stoichiometric ratio of liquid and solid $\gamma = 1$, equation (14) is simplified:

$$W = da/d\tau = K^* \cdot (C_0(1 - \alpha))^n \cdot (1 - \alpha). \quad (15)$$

Processing of experimental data according to equation (15) can be carried out according to the algorithm [12].

3. Conclusions

It is proposed to take into account the function of the distribution of particles of solid material in the form of needles according to their length, and the equation of the speed of the process in the kinetic region of the leaching course is mathematically substantiated. The

first order in a solid material according to a given function of the distribution of the number of particles from the length of the needles is proved.

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